

An observation on twin primes

Emanuele Pace

Italy

email: emanuelepacescrittore@gmail.com

The twin prime conjecture says that there are infinite twin primes.

In this, this conjecture is similar to the theorem asserting the existence of infinite prime numbers, which, as is well known, was first proved by Euclid.

However, in the 19th century, a considerable extension of this theorem was proved and this extension was called the *prime number theorem*. This theorem states that between 1 and any number x there are approximately $x/\ln x$ prime numbers, where $\ln x$ is the natural logarithm of x . And here we come to the formulation of my conjecture concerning twin primes:

There is a formula that can tell us how many twin primes there are between 1 and a given number x .